

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN BMI AND CORONARY ARTERY
DISEASE SEVERITY IN FEMALES OF PAKISTANI ORIGIN**Dr. Shaista Akbar¹, Dr. Samim Azizi², Dr. Madiha Safdar³¹ Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore² Central South University, China³ Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To assess the relationship between BMI and the severity of coronary heart disease in the Pakistani women population.

Project: An Observational cross-sectional study.

Place and duration of the study: In the Department of Cardiology, Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from January 2019 to January 2020.

Patients and methods: 132 women undergoing coronary angiography were included in the study population. Obesity was classified as Normal (BMI 21-24 kg / m²), overweight (BMI 25-29 kg / m²), obesity class I (BMI 30-34) according to BMI according to the criteria of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) kg / m²), obesity class II (BMI 35-39 kg / m² and obesity class III (BMI 40 or more kg / m²).

Coronary angiography data was obtained from Siemens Queries software, which contains a database containing detailed results of angiographic tests of all patients in this institution. Significant lesions were defined as those that narrowed > 70% of the coronary artery diameter (> 50% for the left main coronary artery). We tried to measure "CAD severity" by determining the incidence of high-risk coronary anatomy (HRCA, > 50% left main coronary artery stenosis and / or significant coronary artery disease).

Results: Comparing overall obese (BMI ≥ 30) vs. non obese groups, a statistically significant low prevalence of HRCA was encountered in the obese group (26 of 56, 46.4% vs. 54 of 76, 79.5% p < 0.05) **Conclusion:** We conclude that obesity is associated with less serious coronary heart disease in Pakistani women.

Key words: obesity, coronary artery disease severity, coronary angiography.

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Please cite this article in press Shaista Akbar et al., **Association Between BMI And Coronary Artery Disease Severity In Females Of Pakistani Origin**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular disease is the main cause of women's death. The incidence of coronary heart disease (CAD) increases with age as both sexes progress, but for women, this rate lags behind men by about a decade. Due to their older age, women with CAD are more likely to have comorbidities such as diabetes, obesity and hypertension¹⁻². Obesity itself is associated with conventional cardiovascular risk factors (e.g. hypertension, dyslipidemia and diabetes), new risk factors (e.g. inflammatory markers such as the highly sensitive C-reactive protein [hs-CRP]) and interleukin-6 [IL-6]), 3 and those compounds that are coronary artery endothelial disorders provide a reasonable biological relationship with epidemiological observations showing that obesity is associated with a risk of immortal and lethal cardiovascular events³⁻⁴. In women

Although obesity has been shown to be an independent risk factor for CAD events in the general population, recent data indicate a clear paradoxical relationship between obesity and cardiovascular prognosis in some patient subsets⁵⁻⁶. In particular, the data suggests that short-term results and survival seem paradoxically better in patients with heart failure and in patients after coronary artery bypass grafting. In fact, the subject of the "obesity paradox" has led to considerable controversy in recent literature; An Israeli study examined the relationship between body mass index (BMI) and CAD extension and suggested that obesity is considered a "negative predictor" of coronary artery disease severity in patients reporting for coronary angiography⁷⁻⁸. We are trying to examine this hypothesis in Pakistani women. The purpose of our research is to assess the relationship between BMI and the severity of coronary artery disease in the Pakistani women.

METHOD:

This cross-sectional observational study was held in the Department of Cardiology, Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from January 2019 to January 2020. The study population included 132

Table I:

	Normal / over weight	Obesity I/II/III	P value
Hypertension	42	30	0.8615
Diabetes	32	20	0.4770
Smoking	0	4	0.0304

Comparing the overall obese group (BMI $\geq$ 30) with non-obese groups, statistically significant low risk high risk coronary anatomy (HRCA) was found in the obese group (26 out of 56, 46.4% from 54 76, 79.5% with $p < 0, 05$) table II

women undergoing coronary angiography. Demographic data and patient medical history, including cardiovascular risk factor profile, were summarized from patients' medical records (age, sex, diabetes according to WHO criteria, hypertension according to the criteria of the Joint National Committee 7, smoking and family history of coronary heart disease).

Obesity was classified as normal (BMI 21-24 kg / m²), overweight (BMI 25-29 kg / m²), obesity class I (BMI 30-34) according to BMI according to the criteria of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) kg / m²), obesity class II (BMI 35-39 kg / m² and obesity class III (BMI 40 or more kg / m²).

Coronary angiography data was obtained from Siemens Queries software, which contains a database containing detailed results of angiographic tests of all patients in this institution. Serious injuries were defined as those that narrowed > 70% of the coronary artery diameter (> 50% for the left main coronary artery). We tried to measure "CAD severity" by determining the incidence of high-risk coronary anatomy (HRCA, > 50% left main coronary artery stenosis and / or significant coronary artery disease).

Statistical analysis: Statistical analyzes were performed using the SPSS 16.0 software package (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, Illinois). Continuous data (scale) are presented as mean $\pm$ standard error (SE). Differences in group means were assessed using an independent Student's t-test and a square probability test as well as Fisher's exact test.

RESULTS:

In our study group there were 132 patients with an average age of 57.8 years and an average of 29.4 kg / m² BMI.

Risk factors such as diabetes and hypertension were more common in obese women than in normal and overweight women, as shown in Table I.

Table II:
P – Value 0.006

	Mild/Moderate CAD	Severe CAD
	Normal Coronaries/Minor CAD/Subcritical CAD	SVCAD/DVCAD/ TVCAD
Normal/Over weight	22 (20.5%)	54(79.5%)
Obesity I/II/III	30.(53.7%)	26(46.4%)

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of obesity is increasing worldwide, Pakistan is no exception. According to the National Health Survey of 2001, the incidence of obesity in the 25-64 age group in Pakistan is 13% for men and 23% for women⁹⁻¹⁰. Obesity has traditionally been considered a cardiovascular risk factor and is associated with an increased risk of CAD and mortality in the general population, including women. Therefore, it can be assumed that obese patients should have worse results than their non-obese counterparts; however, recent publications suggest that obesity may actually be associated with better outcomes in CAD patients undergoing revascularization¹¹⁻¹². Our findings show that obese patients who report for coronary angiography have paradoxically lower CAD load and a higher risk of coronary anatomy becoming widespread (significant left or triple vascular disease) compared to non-obese comparators. The prevalence of diabetes and hypertension, which implies the presence of a clear "obesity paradox". The "WIZE" study showed that normal weight women with metabolic syndrome significantly increase cardiovascular risk. Similarly, obese and overweight women with normal metabolism have a relatively low cardiovascular risk¹³. Although obese patients were found to have a lower CAD burden and severity of injury, these results were ameliorated because obese patients were referred for early coronary angiography. Although our observations are speculative, it means "physician bias or bias" for obese patients (especially those with additional cardiovascular risk factors) for more liberal angiography; the lower threshold of the decision to define coronary anatomy, probably due to clear symptoms, disability and the frequent occurrence of comorbidities in overweight patients.

Another possible explanation for this finding is that BMI does not measure the size or ratio of subcutaneous visceral fat in a particular person to identify overweight and obesity. The visceral fat area associated with insulin resistance appears to be

an important link between many components of the metabolic syndrome such as dyslipidemia and hypertension. In addition, its relationship does not distinguish between visceral abdominal fat deposits, using weight and waist circumference measurements that can provide clinically useful estimates of the ratio of upper body or abdominal fat¹⁴. Therefore, mass status classification based on routine measurements may underestimate the role of visceral fat distribution in predicting cardiovascular risk. Physical inactivity, socioeconomic factors etc. Although there are other potentially confusing variables such as this could affect our results, these data have not been investigated because they are not readily available. Traditional risk factors, viz. Hypertension and diabetes were not analyzed independently because of their high incidence in the group of obese patients. Therefore, despite the increased prevalence of hypertension and diabetes, obese women had less severe coronary artery disease, and the paradox in the female population studied further deepened the theory of obesity¹⁵. In our research population, the apparent negative relationship between obesity and the severity of coronary heart disease appears to primarily reflect medical practice models, especially young age for coronary angiography of obese patients. You cannot ignore the cohort selection error, a cohort study carried out by one institution. Finally, although our results cannot be reflected in the general population, they seem to generate hypotheses and deserve future discoveries in a larger multicenter study.

CONCLUSION:

We conclude that obesity is associated with a less serious coronary artery disease in Pakistani women.

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